

MAGIC

Marginal lands for Growing Industrial Crops

Deliverable reference number and title:

D2.4 – MAP-DB (version 3)

Due date of deliverable: December 2020

Actual submission date: 2 March 2021

Lead beneficiary

Wageningen Research (WR)
P.O.Box 47
6700 AA Wageningen
The Netherlands

Beneficiaries website: www.alterra.nl

Responsible Author

Berien Elbersen	Wageningen Research	Berien.elbersen@wur.nl	+31653728652
Michiel van Eupen	Wageningen Research	michiel.vaneupen@wur.nl	+31317481646

Additional Authors

Ian McCallum	IIASA	mccallum@iiasa.ac.at	+43(0)2236 807-328
--------------	-------	----------------------	--------------------

Type

R	Document, report	<input type="checkbox"/>
DEM	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	<input type="checkbox"/>
DEC	Websites, patent fillings, videos, etc.	<input type="checkbox"/>
OTHER		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Dissemination Level

PU	Public	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	<input type="checkbox"/>

Horizon 2020
European Union Funding
for Research & Innovation

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No. 727698.

The sole responsibility for the content of this publication lies with the authors. It does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the Research Executive Agency (REA) or the European Commission (EC). REA or the EC are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

Table of contents

- 1 Publishable executive summary 4
- 2 Introduction 5
- 3 Access to MAP-DB version 2 in ESRI..... 6
 - 3.1 Explanation of what is in the MAP-DB 6

Publishable executive summary

Several studies agree on the existence of a considerable amount of land in Europe deemed less favourable for conventional agriculture. This land has been either abandoned because of its productivity, or it is used as grassland. MAGIC is based on the premise that cultivation of selected industrial crops on areas facing natural constraints (e.g. extreme climatic conditions, low soil productivity, steep slope, etc.) can i) ensure the production of resource-efficient feedstocks, with low indirect land-use change (iLUC), for a growing bio-based industry, and ii) increase farmers' incomes through access to new markets and the revalorization of marginal land.

MAGIC Deliverable D2.4 – presents a third prototype of the MAGIC-Maps tool. It aims to provide user friendly access to the mapped marginal lands as elaborated in the MAGIC project. What is new in this third version as compared to the former version is the spatial detail at which the marginal land data are displayed and the inclusion of Ukraine. The marginal land area can now be consulted at the LAU I and II level which is municipal level in most countries, and this is a much more spatially detailed level than the Nuts 2/3 level used in the former prototype versions.

To access the version 3 MAP-DB containing the Marginal land Agri-environmental zonation (MAEZ) goto link: [Magic – Marginal Lands for Growing Industrial Crops \(magic-h2020.eu\)](http://magic-h2020.eu) (scroll down to MAGIC databases).

1 Introduction

This document explains access and contents of the third version of the database of the Marginal land map (MAP-DB, version 3) which was made available to project partners and also external users in Month 38 of the MAGIC project.

2 Access to MAP-DB version 2 in ESRI

To access the ESRI viewing tool for MAEZ open underneath link:

[Magic – Marginal Lands for Growing Industrial Crops \(magic-h2020.eu\)](http://magic-h2020.eu)

If the link does not work copy it and paste it in the webbrowser address bar.

When you open the ESRI tool you will see Figure 1:

Figure 1: View after opening the link and explanation of icons (In the clouds the functions of the icons are explained)

Further details on the elaboration and results of the Marginal land mapping can be obtained from D2.6 and also from D4.1 where the use of the Marginal land mapping data is described for selection of test sites and crop types (See Magic website under deliverables tab).

2.1 Explanation of what is in the MAP-DB

This app contains maps of drivers of marginal land information for Europe by Local Administrative Units (LAU) class, and for the Ukraine at the Administrative Level 2.

For more information on the methodology behind these maps, please see Mapping Marginal Land Deliverable 2.6.

The maps contain attribute fields in the database which indicate which identify the drivers of marginality:

- KM2_CHEMIC km2 marginality type CHEMICAL

- KM2_CLIMAT km2 marginality type CLIMATE
- KM2_FERTIL km2 marginality type FERTILITY
- KM2_ROOTIN km2 marginality type ROOTING
- KM2_TERRAI km2 marginality type TERRAIN
- KM2_WETNES km2 marginality type WETNESS
- KM2_AREA km2 of unit
- KM2_AGRI km2 Agricultureal Area
- KM2_MARG km2 Total Marginal Area
- PERC_MARG % Total Marginal Area (relative to agric. area)

The maps have been shaded based upon their percent marginality in relation to agricultural area. This agricultural area includes all land that was classified in an agricultural land cover class in at least one of the four Corine Land Cover versions (1990, 2000, 2006, 2012).

The user may select any polygon on the map to visualize the data behind the map. The full attribute tables can be accessed at the bottom of the screen by clicking on the arrow button.

Additional widgets are available at the top of the screen for the map legend, layer list and basemap.